

Assurance of security and order of grassroots political system of religious areas of Nghe an province, Vietnam

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ABSTRACT: Ensuring social order and security in general and religious areas in particular is the most important task of governments at all levels and the entire political system in each locality nationwide. Nghe An province, Vietnam is a locality with many religious followers. For recent years, in general, religious organizations in the province have built the orientations of their religious activities under the law, built all-people great unity bloc, maintained political stability, created a great motivation in economic and social development. Currently, in the context of the world, regional and domestic situation, there are many complicated and unpredictable developments, many new problems in religious activities, therefore, it's required that the government and the whole political system of religious area needs to bring into full play their roles to ensure social order and security, especially religious security issues.

KEYWORDS: Security and order, religious area, Nghe An, religion, political system.

1. INTRODUCTION

The religious area political system is an important component of the general political system, is the executive level, directly organizes and mobilizes the masses to implement the Party's line, policies and laws of the State in order to strengthen and bring into play the strength of the all-people great unity bloc, creating a great motivation in socio-economic development, maintaining political stability and consolidating the all-people national defense and people's security at the grassroots. In Nghe An, for recent years, the political system at the grassroots level in religious area has brought into full play its role despite of also revealing many limitations, many complicated issues of security and order arising, especially in relation to religious security issues. On the basis of evaluating the general actual situation, the article proposes a number of solutions to enhance the security and order of the political system of the religious area in Nghe An province, Vietnam.

2. RESULTS

2.1. Actual situation of ensuring security and order of the political system of religious area at the grassroots level in Nghe An province

Result of ensuring security and order of the political system of religious area in Nghe An province

Up to now, in Nghe An province, there are two legally recognized religions, namely Catholicism and Buddhism, with a total number of followers of about 300,000 people (accounting for about 10% of the province's population). In which, Catholicism is mainly distributed in 15/21 districts, cities and towns; 214 communes, wards and townships (accounting for 44.6% of total number of communes in the province); 897/942 hamlets with 15% parishioners. Nghe An Catholics are mainly concentrated in Yen Thanh, Quynh Luu, Nghi Loc, Dien Chau districts, Cua Lo Town, Vinh City. Buddhism currently has had about 2.6 thousand followers, 24 temples, 25 monks (including 8 nuns and abbots).

For the past years, in order to bring into full play the role of grassroots political system in religious area in ensuring political security, social order and safety, the Provincial Party Committee and People's Committee of Nghe An province have promptly directed Party committees and local governments to proactively set up Steering Committees and supporting sub-committees to track, advise and urge the implementation of building and promoting the role of the grassroots political system in religious area, consider this as one of the key tasks to gather and solve difficulties and problems for the mass, build religious unity bloc, ensure political security, social order and safety and successfully implement industrialization and modernization cause of the country.

On the basis of thoroughly grasping the guidelines of the Party, the policies and laws of the State, guidelines and directives of the Provincial Party Committee, the Provincial People's Committee and superior departments, boards and branches on religion and

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religious affairs work, the grassroots political system in religious areas of Nghe An province has proactively carried out many synchronous solutions, gradually improving the efficiency of regional socio-economic development, especially ensuring security and order, specifically:

Firstly, pay attention to and promote education, propaganda and dissemination of the Party's guidelines and policies, the laws of the State and local guidelines in the religious area. It is identified that this is a leading solution for parishioners to understand, thoroughly grasp and fully implement the guidelines and policies on ensuring freedom of belief and religion of the Party and the State; and at the same time fully exercise the rights and obligations of citizens towards the country. In order to put propaganda and education into reality, many districts and towns established groups and teams to strengthen the building of grassroots building, closely stick to the locality, proactively advise the Party committees and authorities to consolidate and build the grassroots political system; promptly grasp and resolve the legitimate aspirations and interests of the parishioners, conflicts and frustrations among the mass as well as activities of hostile forces taking advantage of them to oppose the government, disturb security and order at the grassroots in order to proactively prevent and coordinate in the struggle, so as not to become hot spots. Party committees and authorities at all levels are interested in investing in building material facilities and means and diversifying forms of propaganda. Coordinate with the provincial and district police forces to regularly follow the locality, participate in propaganda, advocacy, grasp the situation, advise and direct the problem solving at the grassroots level, to avoid the occurrence of hot spots on security and order in the religious area; coordinate with the Committee for Religious Affairs of the Department of Home Affairs, the Military Command, the Provincial Border Guard... to open many training courses on knowledge of defense and security, thoroughly grasp legal documents on belief and religion for religious dignitaries, officers and officials doing religious work of the district and grassroots levels as well as people.

Secondly, direct the good implementation of admitting party members in religious areas, and at the same time increasing number of party members to attend the meetings in villages where there are no or not enough party members to establish a party cell. Up to now, localities such as Vinh City, Dien Chau District, Yen Thanh, Do Luong, Nghi Loc, Quynh Luu, and Cua Lo Town have proactively developed schemes and actively implemented the development of party members in religious areas. In addition, focus on creating resources and building a team of officers who are religious people. Determine that this is an important measure to build and promote the role of the grassroots political system in religious areas in the province. The Party committees at all levels advocated discovering and putting into main sources of officers who are religious people at grassroots level, annually add to the planning and implement the training and retraining of religious officers. However, up to now, this work has not been really effective and encountered many difficulties.

Thirdly, arrange and consolidate the team of officers and well implement the regimes and policies for the team specialized in religious work. This is the force that plays a pivotal role, taking care of the community's interests, grasping the thoughts and aspirations of the parishioners, the center of religious solidarity; take the lead in implementing and proactively mobilizing parishioners to well observe the guidelines of the Party and the laws of the State.

Fourthly, proactively renovate the content and leadership methods of the Party committees and cells of religious areas in the direction of promoting democracy, promoting collective wisdom in leadership activities, sticking to reality and specificity of each locality. A number of party organizations have developed thematic resolutions on measures to lead and direct economic, cultural and social development; maintain security - national defense. The grassroots local governments in the religious areas have had many innovations in administration, proactively guided and managed religious activities in accordance with the law. Many communes, wards and townships focus on administrative reform, well implement the grassroots democracy regulations, improve the quality of citizen reception, settled complaints and denunciations; organize mediation, people's inspection, settle cases right from the moment they arise, so as not to let complicated developments and generate hot spots. The Fatherland Front and socio-political organizations in the religious area have many innovations in content and form of activities such as club activities, arts and sports, thematic movements to gather members and propaganda and mobilization of people in the religious areas.

Limitations of ensuring security and order of the grassroots political system in religious areas of Nghe An province

Besides the achieved results, the operation of the grassroots political system in religious area of Nghe An province also revealed many weaknesses and inadequacies such as:

Actual situation of security and order in the religious areas of Nghe An province is still often complicated, especially: the illegal occupation of state land to build worshipping works, religious works; gathering of a large number of people for claims and lawsuits; illegal division, establishment of parishes, religious sects, transfer or appointment of priests, performance of rituals outside the prescribed scope. Some reactionary organizations show signs of connecting with Catholic dignitaries to organize and direct protest activities, especially before the time of many important events in the country. Some extremist priests and dignitaries take advantage of religion to isolate party members and leaders in religious areas, force party members in religious areas to voluntarily resign from the Party, and prevent some progressive parishioners from participating in the social works, not allow parishioners to join the party, obstruct them from performing their civic duties, even engaging in acts of opposing or challenging the government, inciting parishioners to disrupt security and order, arresting people illegally, opposing official duty executors; distorting the guidelines and lines of the Party, policies and laws of the State; inciting the parishioners not to participate in State

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duties, typically the case at Quan Lang parish, Anh Son in 2012; Trai Gao, Nghi Phuong, Nghi Loc in 2013 or An Hoa, Song Ngoc, and Quynh Luu in 2016 and 2017.

The main cause comes from the lack of knowledge of the people, the induction and incitement of some extremist priests, the conspiracy of hostile forces to take advantage of religious issues to oppose the government and significantly partially from the weakness and limitations of the grassroots political system.

Propaganda, dissemination and thorough grasping of the Party's line, the State's policies and laws, directives of the Provincial Party Committee, the Provincial People's Committee, especially the policy on religion are still slow and no synchronization and not high efficiency; the mobilization of followers to participate in the all-people movement of protecting national security is still formal and perfunctory; activities of the Fatherland Front and socio-political organizations in social criticism, assurance of legitimate rights and interests of parishioners, gathering and mobilization of the mass to ensure security the order is still overlapping, blurred, not really grasping the thoughts and aspirations of people in a timely manner and lacking initiative when complex issues of religious security arise in the area; the development of party members of religious origin and training of human resources with expertise in the field of religion faces many difficulties; coordination with superior agencies and units takes place slowly, lacks synchronization and rigor, leading to the fact that issues of security and order arising often lasts long and becomes complicated; especially when a hot spot arises in the area, someone considers it the duty of the people's police force, so the spirit and responsibility of the whole political system for participating in solving the problem is not high and not drastic. The work of capturing and taking advantage of the role of prestigious people in religion is still slow, there is a lack of consensus on viewpoints and methods of advocacy, and the role of the commune police force in timely grasping and handling conflicts arising in the hearts of the people are still blurred...

Therefore, the security and order situation in religious area of Nghe An province has recently continued to record unstable and unpredictable developments, with an increasing scale and number of cases, and increasingly complex nature, a potential risk of going beyond the control of the grassroots political system. In fact, up to now, when complicated cases occur in the locality, the grassroots political system is often unable to control, even inactive, fails to promote its role, becoming the focus that hostile forces aim to destroy.

2.2. Solutions to enhance security and order of the grassroots political system in religious areas of Nghe An province

Firstly, organize to thoroughly grasp and raise awareness for officers and party members of religious areas to understand the guidelines and lines of the Party, policies and laws of the State on religion; Objectives and guidelines of the Party Committee and Provincial Authority, especially the awareness of Resolution No. 18/NQ - TU in 2004 on strengthening and building grassroots political systems in ethnic minority and religious areas; Conclusion No. 09/KL - TU 2006 on building the grassroots political system in religious areas; Directive No. 20 on continuing to promote Conclusion No. 09/KL - TU; Directive No. 172/CT - People's Committee - NC dated October 25, 2014 on promoting the all-people movement of national security protection in areas of ethnic minorities in Nghe An province; Scheme No. 01/DA – TU dated August 10, 2016 on building party cells and developing party members in blocks, hamlets and villages without Party cells, and blocks, hamlets and villages at risk of no party cells and members. At the same time, promote the propaganda of the Party's guidelines, policies and laws of the State to the mass in religious areas, with emphasis on the law on belief and religion for the mass to understand and strictly comply with policies and laws, avoid being exploited by hostile forces to oppose the government.

Secondly, step up the work of building the Party, reorganizing and renovating the operating method and working style of the Party committees, authorities, the Fatherland Fronts and socio-political organizations. Continue to build and reorganize weak grassroots cells, develop party members of religious origin, build party committees, grassroots part cells to really become leadership nucleus for the religious area movement; eliminate the situation of not having enough party members to establish party committees and socio-political organizations; strengthen the implementation of the grassroots democracy ordinance, resolutely struggle with criticism and self-criticism, boldly eliminate officers who are degraded in morality, quality, weak in professional skills, and lose credibility in front of the public. Supplement, finalize and well implement operation statutes, promote democracy among the people.

Thirdly, improve the operating efficiency of state management of religion, focus on fostering and improving the quality of grassroots officers. Especially the work of land management, basic construction in religious areas, timely settle legitimate demands of the congregation and parishioners for the construction of worshipping works on the basis of strictly complying with the Land law. Proactively review and detect shortcomings in socio-economic management, conflicts within the people to take measures to rectify and overcome. Proactively grasp the people's thoughts and legitimate aspirations to solve and respond in a timely manner, so as not to let someone take advantage of religion to incite parishioners to oppose the government, split religion and sabotage the all-people great unity bloc. Well implement the officer planning, strengthen training and retraining and use of Catholic officers. Have policies to attract good officers to the grassroots organization; carry out rotation of promising young officers to the grassroots units for fostering and training through practice. Encourage and receive new graduates to voluntarily

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come back to work for the commune, especially the religious area to create a long-term source of staff. It's needed to have a clear mechanism for clear coordination, assignment and responsibility division.

Fourthly, step up the building of all-people movement of national security protection in religious areas. This is a strategic work, an important foundation, deciding the success or failure of the mission of protecting security and order in the area and fighting against the plots and activities of hostile forces taking advantage of religion. In order for the movement to become substantive and highly effective, it is necessary to focus on eradicating impressions, prejudices and inferiority complex that separates the parishioners; clearly understand, firmly grasp the psychological characteristics, appreciate the true nature, respect the legitimate demands, religious beliefs and sentiments of the parishioners; identify the parishioners as citizens. On that basis, proactively reach out to the believers in an open, reliable, close and respectful manner, thereby propagating and educating them to understand the Party's guidelines, policies and laws of the State. It is necessary to find any way for the parishioners to see that respect for God and patriotism are not contradictory. On the other hand, it is necessary to continue to emphasize that, with activities taking advantage of religion to sabotage the revolutionary cause, prevent followers from performing their civic duties, adversely affecting the policy of great national unity, damaging to the healthy culture and morality of the nation. It's required to fight and unmask in an unforgivable manner. In the form of advocacy, in addition to organizing propaganda, meeting and learning activities for the majority, it is necessary to pay attention to the specific form of advocacy of the core forces of the religious areas who are knowledgeable about the movement, clearly understand the practical value of the movement, who are reputable with the parishioners in both "life" and "religious affairs"; and a team of clerical dignitaries, because the parishioners believe very much and obey bishops and priests in both religious and secular affairs. In fact, the places where the result of mobilizing dignitaries and clergies to agree, support and encourage the movement have the movement developed widely among the parishioners, proactively grasp the situation and timely solve the complex problems in the locality. Mobilizing the parishioners to build a movement of all people, all people protect the national security of the religious areas must apply many forms and methods that are rich and practical, associated with the needs and interests, and in accordance with the concept of religious morality of the parishioners in close coordination with other movements such as: people's security group, self-governing group, council of security and order protection, building safe wards and communes, safe parishes...

Fifthly, the Party committees, authorities, departments, branches and grassroots organizations must try to meet the legitimate needs in the lives of parishioners. Doing this job well will have a fundamental impact, follow the rule and give rise to good affection for the social regime, form and further deepen the attachment to the revolution, to the nation, to socialism in the hearts of followers. This interest must pay attention to many different aspects, including focusing on a number of fields such as: invest in developing economy, solve job needs, increase production, expand industries, improve labor productivity; do hunger eradication, poverty alleviation, increase income, build infrastructure, satisfy demand for electricity, roads, schools and stations; satisfy demands of material life, spiritual culture, religious activities such as worshipping places, worshipers, baptism for parishioners, parishioners study the bible, catechism, religious law and pray, join congregation's organizations, thereby making the material, spiritual and cognitive life of the parishioners become improved, reflecting the superiority of the regime, so that the mass can actively participate in the construction of the homeland and live a "good and beautiful life" in religion, respecting the God and expressing patriotism".

Sixthly, focus on leading and directing the commune police force, promoting the role of the police force in protecting security and order in religious areas. Accelerate the arrangement of regular police forces to work in communes, wards and townships, especially in key areas related to security and order. In order to promote its role well as a core force in protecting security and order, the commune police force needs to continue to innovate and improve work efficiency. Do well the work of advising the Party committees and authorities of communes and townships on security work in religious areas; well perform the state management of security and order in the locality; serve as the core for the all-people movement of national security protection in the religious areas; proactively prevent, detect and fight against manifestations that may arise in terms of security in the locality; perform basic operations work to fight to unmask the plots and tricks of hostile forces to take advantage of religion to infringe on national security, incite the mass to demonstrate against the government, let the public clearly see the face, lower their prestige before the mass.

Seventhly, regularly preliminarily review and summarize to learn experience from activities of each organization in the grassroots political system in the religious areas in association with the assessment and classification of party organizations, the Fatherland Front and the unions, thereby serving as a basis for setting out the programs, missions and solutions of the following year.

3. CONCLUSION

Under the forecast of economic and social researchers, the world, regional and domestic situation continues to have many complicated and unpredictable developments, the work of ensuring security and order in the religious areas of the grassroots political system will face many difficulties and challenges, and the grassroots political system will continue to become the focal point of opposition of hostile forces. Therefore, in order to promote its role well, the grassroots political system in religious areas of Nghe An province, Vietnam needs to continue to synchronously and effectively implement the above solutions.

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